

Table 1: Mapping of rights and correlation between laws.

LGPD	GDPR	ADPPA	Privacy Act	CCPA
Minimized collection	✓ Data Minimization	✓ Data Minimization	✓ Collection of requested personal information	✓ Right to Limit Use and Disclosure of Sensitive Personal Information
Confirmation of Existence of Treatment	✓ Right of access by the data subject	×	✓ Access to personal date	✓ Right to Know What Personal Information is Being Collected. Right to Access Personal Information
Data Access	✓ Right of access by the data subject	Right to Access	✓ Right to Access	✓ Right to Know What Personal Information is Being Collected. Right to Access Personal Information
Data correction	✓ Right to rectification	✓ Right to Correct	✓ Right to Correct	✓ Right to Correct Inaccurate Personal Information
Anonymization	✓ Pseudonymization	×	✓ Anonymity and pseudonymity	×
Data portability	✓ Right to data portability	✓ Right to Portability	×	✓ Right to Know What Personal Information is Being Collected. Right to Access Personal Information
Data deletion	✓ Right to erasure	✓ Right to Delete	×	✓ Right to Delete Personal Information
Information on Participating Entities	✓ Information to be provided where personal data are collected from the data subject	✓ Right of Transparency	✓ Open and transparent management of personal information	✓ Right to Know What Personal Information is Sold or Shared and to Whom
Information on the Possibility of Not Consenting	✓ Right to withdraw	✓ Right of Transparency	×	✓ Right to Opt Out of Sale or Sharing of Personal Information
Revocation of Consent	✓ Right to withdraw	✓ Right to Consent and Object	✓ Collection of requested personal information / Use or disclosure of personal information	✓ Right to Opt Out of Sale or Sharing of Personal Information
Dispute	✓ Right to contest / Right to lodge a complaint with a supervisory authority	✓ Right to Consent and Object	×	✓ Right to Opt Out of Sale or Sharing of Personal Information
Purpose Consistent Processing	✓ Storage limitation	✓ Data Minimization	✓ Use or disclosure of personal information	✓ Right to Know What Personal Information is Being Collected. Right to Access Personal Information
Retention Consistent with Purpose	✓ Storage limitation	✓ Data Retention policies	✓ Security of personal information	×
Opposition to Automated Decision Making	✓ Automated individual decision-making, including profiling	×	×	×

Processing Restriction	✓ Right to restriction of processing	×	×	✓ Right to Limit Use and Disclosure of Sensitive Personal Information
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Table 2: Mapping of LGPD rights and correlation between frameworks.

LGPD	Privacy by Design	ISO/IEC 29100
Minimized collection	✓ Proactive not Reactive; Preventative not Remedial / Privacy as the Default Setting / Privacy Embedded into Design [44]	✓ Data minimization [23]
Confirmation of Existence of Treatment	✓ Visibility and Transparency [44]	✓ Openness, transparency and notice [44]
Data Access	✓ Visibility and Transparency [44]	✓ Individual participation and access [44]
Data correction	× [23]	✓ Individual participation and access [44]
Anonymization	× [23]	✓ Use, retention and disclosure limitation [23]
Data portability	✓ Respect for User Privacy [44]	✓ Use, retention and disclosure limitation [23]
Data deletion	× [23]	✓ Individual participation and access
Information on Participating Entities	✓ Visibility and Transparency [44]	✓ Openness, transparency and notice [44]
Information on the Possibility of Not Knowing	✓ Visibility and Transparency [44]	✓ Consent and choice [44]
Revocation of the Consentation	✓ Proactive not Reactive; Preventative not Remedial / Respect for User Privacy [44]	✓ Consent and choice [44]
Dispute	✓ Respect for User Privacy [44]	✓ Accountability [44]
Purpose Consistent Processing	✓ Privacy as The Default Setting [44]	✓ Collection limitation [14], [44]
Retention Consistent with Purpose	✓ Respect for User Privacy [23], [44]	✓ Use, retention and disclosure limitation
Opposition to Automated Decision Making	✓ Respect for User Privacy [44]	× [44]
Processing Restriction	✓ Proactive not Reactive; Preventative not Remedial [44]	× [44]